

UTILIZING DIGITAL MIND MAPPING APPLICATION IN ENHANCING STUDENTS' IMMEDIATE ACHIEVEMENT AND KNOWLEDGE RETENTION

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the immediate achievement and knowledge retention levels among students who utilize the digital mind mapping application and to ascertain the effect of utilizing digital mind mapping on students' immediate achievement level in terms of pretest and direct post-test, as well as on students' knowledge retention level in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test. This research study employed a one-shot pretest-posttest pre-experimental research design. Data were gathered from thirty-six (36) seventh-grade students of Tongantongan National High School through pretest, direct post-test, and delayed post-test questionnaires. The data were subjected to descriptive statistics such as the mean, percentage and frequency and analyzed using Paired t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study revealed that the students have poor immediate achievement level and knowledge retention level. Furthermore, the paired t-test analysis showed that there is a significant difference in students' immediate achievement level in terms of pretest and direct post-test, and there is also significant difference in students' knowledge retention level in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test. It indicates that despite the students' poor achievement and retention level, the utilization of the digital mind mapping application has a positive effect on enhancing students' ability to acquire and retain knowledge. The overall result encourages higher authority, curriculum experts, and educators to leverage technology and consider utilizing digital mind mapping application as a method in optimizing the students' achievement and retention level.

Keywords: *digital mind map, immediate achievement, knowledge retention*

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century marks a remarkable shift in education, where learning and teaching intertwine with the dynamic pace of innovation and technology. It's an era where classrooms extend beyond four walls into a digital realm of endless possibilities. With the ever-changing world of technology, classrooms are gaining more technology and having to incorporate it into student learning. As education becomes more digitized, using technological tools to organize educational content becomes critical to the success of education (Arisoy, 2022).

One of the problems that stimulated the making of this study is the poor academic achievement scores and declining student retention rates within the Filipino student population. According to the 2018 PISA International Report, Filipino students scored an average of 353 points in mathematical literacy, which is notably less than the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) average of 489 points, indicating a below Level 1 proficiency (OECD, 2019). The 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), assessed the performance of Grade four students in math and science proficiency, it ended up with the lowest rank out of the 58 countries that were part of the study (Sison, 2022). These achievement tests are heavily influenced by the students' effectiveness to attain and retain knowledge. As student teachers, these findings are very visible in the classroom setting, especially the students of Tongantongan National High School. Prior to the conduct of study, students showed an unsatisfying academic performance especially in achieving the intended learning outcomes and retaining knowledge. With an average percentage mean score of 43 percent, a total of 140 Grade-7 students did not meet the expectation in their summative test on the topic Motion in One Dimension. This result is alarming because Grade 7 students, as the first year in high school curriculum, are expected to grasp fundamental concepts pivotal to subsequent high school curricular progression.

In the context of education, immediate achievement refers to the initial and tangible outcomes or knowledge gained shortly by the learners after engaging a new learning experience while retention is the person's ability to remember information they have learned, whether it is for a short or extended duration (Bawaneh, 2019). Instead of memorizing, educators want their students to retain knowledge spanning for more than a week after the implementation of innovation, intervention, or strategy (Akanbi et al., 2021; Meyer et al., 2019; Granito & Chernobilsky, 2012). When the students struggle to meet the learning outcomes and retain essential knowledge in Mathematics and Science, it not only affects their test scores but also impedes their ability to advance in these subjects, leading to lower international rankings.

In connection to this problem, educators are actively exploring strategies to assist students in transferring knowledge from their short-term memory to their long-term memory (Valderama & Oligo, 2021). One of the solutions is the integration of an effective

note-taking strategy such as Mind mapping developed by Tony Buzan in 1974. A mind map is a graphical representation of a topic or idea that aids in the teaching and learning process in the classroom (Anas et al., 2018). Mind mapping highlights the necessary facts and overall structure of a subject. Mind mapping helps an individual see connections and provide overview of key points. Several studies implied the significant effects of mind mapping in enhancing students' academic performance especially in Physics subject (Akanbi et al., 2021; Bawaneh, 2019).

This action research aims to discover the effects of the implementation of Digital Mind Mapping as instructional strategies to enhance the learners' acquisition and retention of knowledge, ultimately fostering better educational outcomes for Filipino students. The results and findings of this study will be beneficial in the field of education, considering the evident poor academic achievements and declining students' retention rate in the country which lead to poor academic performances. Thus, the schools' administrators and teachers will be guided on what to emphasize and utilize in order to increase students' immediate achievement and retention rate in improving their academic performance and life-long success.

The purpose of this study was to determine the immediate achievement and knowledge retention levels among the students exposed to digital mind mapping application, assess the statistical significant difference of the students' immediate achievement level in terms of pretest and direct post-test, and ascertain the statistical significant difference of the students' knowledge retention level in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test. The research was conducted at Tongantongan National High School with Grade 7 Archimedes students serving as the primary research participants.

Research Questions

This action research generally aims to investigate the effect of the utilization of digital mind mapping application in enhancing students' immediate achievement and knowledge retention. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the immediate achievement level of students exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test?
2. What is the level of knowledge retention of the students exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test?
3. Is there a significant difference on students' immediate achievement level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test?
4. Is there a significant difference on students' knowledge retention level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test?

Hypotheses

To answer the stated problems, the study aims to test the following null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference on students' immediate achievement level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference on students' knowledge retention level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test.

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was implemented within the premises of Tongantongan National High School, which is located at P-8, Tongantongan, Valencia City, Bukidnon.

Sampling Method

A purposive sampling method was utilized in identifying the research participants. The students observed were the Grade-7 Archimedes students, with overall 36 participants, taking Physics subject focusing on the topic of Waves particularly the types of waves and anatomy of waves. The researchers chose Grade 7 students, the first year in high school curriculum, as they are expected to grasp fundamental concepts pivotal to subsequent high school curricular progression.

Innovation and Intervention

The innovation of this action research is to investigate the effect of using digital mind mapping application in enhancing students' immediate achievement and knowledge retention. The digital mind mapping application employed was the Nice Mind Application, an offline application that can be downloaded from the Play Store freely. This application was selected because of its accessibility, smooth navigation features, pre-designed templates, customization options, and intuitive and user-friendly interface. In this study, the phases of implementation of the digital mind mapping application to the students were modified from the study of Bawaneh (2019) as follows:

1. Pre-Intervention Assessment – The students underwent a pretest to assess their baseline knowledge before taking the topic about the types and anatomy of waves.
2. Introduction of the Innovation – Digital mind mapping application was introduced and taught to the students including its purpose, key elements, examples, and steps-by-step process.

3. Assisted Intervention –The students, along with the teacher created digital mind maps based on previous lesson, which served as examples.
4. Independent Practice – The students independently practiced utilizing the mind mapping application. They were given homework to create digital mind maps about the types and anatomy of waves. During the class discussion, students used their pre-made mind maps as means of instructional materials.
5. Feedback Session – This phase also highlighted the process of providing feedback to students based on their independent practice. Some of the mind maps contained misconceptions that need to be corrected. Students were given time to revise and modify their prepared mind maps during the class discussion.
6. Post-Intervention Assessment – After all sessions, the students took a direct post-test to assess the outcome or changes resulting from the utilization of the digital mind mapping application. Four weeks after the implementation of the intervention, students underwent a delayed post-test to ascertain the effect of using mind mapping in students' retention level.

Data Collection Method

In this study, the researchers used pre-test, direct post-test, and delayed post-test questionnaires. Before conducting the research, the researchers provided the participants with consent forms to ensure their voluntary participation and to safeguard their rights throughout the research process. The subject was Physics taken by seventh-grade students at Tongantongan National High School. The questionnaires were disseminated among the participants, who were required to respond both prior to and subsequent to the teaching process and planned intervention.

Research Instrument

The researchers employed a 20-item questionnaire modified from the learners' textbook and was verified by the corresponding Cooperating Teacher and School Principal. Table of Specifications was provided to ensure the validity of the said test questionnaire. These questionnaires were designed to capture comprehensive insights into the students' immediate achievement and knowledge retention, spanning a scope of areas relevant to the topic of Waves.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the pretest, direct post-test, and delayed post-test were subjected to descriptive statistics analysis, such as mean, percentage and frequency, to interpret the students' level of immediate achievement and knowledge retention. The students' immediate achievement level and knowledge retention level will be interpreted by adopting the DepEd Order No. 8 series of 2015 grading scale, as presented in table 1 and table 2. The scaling has minimal modifications including the range of raw scores that was adopted from the study of Ollero (2023) and qualitative interpretation from the study of Dumale and Gurat (2023).

Table 1. Qualitative Scale of the Students' Immediate Achievement

Raw Score	Grading Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
16.8-20.0	90-100	Outstanding	Outstanding IA
15.2-16.7	85-89	Very Satisfactory	Very satisfying IA
13.6-15.1	80-84	Satisfactory	Satisfying IA
12.0-13.5	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Fairly satisfying IA
0.00-11.9	Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Poor IA

Legend: IA – Immediate Achievement

Table 2. Qualitative Scale of the Students' Knowledge Retention

Raw Score	Grading Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
16.8-20.0	90-100	Outstanding	Outstanding KR
15.2-16.7	85-89	Very Satisfactory	Very Satisfying KR
13.6-15.1	80-84	Satisfactory	Satisfying KR
12.0-13.5	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfying KR
0.00-11.9	Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Poor KR

Legend: KR – Knowledge Retention

A paired t-test was then utilized to ascertain the presence of any statistically significant differences between the students' pretest-posttest results following exposure to digital mind mapping applications, specifically in the context of enhancing immediate achievement and knowledge retention. This statistical device was employed to test the following hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance: there is no significant difference in students' immediate achievement level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test; and there is no significant difference in students' knowledge retention level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test.

Scope and Limitation

This action research employed a one-shot pretest-posttest pre-experimental research design in order to investigate the effect of utilizing digital mind mapping application in enhancing students' immediate achievement and knowledge retention. The purposively selected participants are the thirty-six (36) seventh-grade students of Tongantongan National High School. Moreover, the intervention utilized only one digital mind mapping application which the Nice Mind Application. The researchers followed a systematic procedure in implementing the intervention using the modified phases of Bawaneh (2019). Furthermore, the data gathered through pre-test, direct post-test, and delayed post-test using the verified 20-item questionnaire, spanning a scope limited only to the types of waves and anatomy of waves. These questionnaires were designed to capture comprehensive insights into the students' immediate achievement and knowledge retention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part presents the students' immediate achievement level and knowledge retention level after the exposure to Digital Mind Mapping Application. It includes the Inferential Analysis in order to conclude the structured hypotheses.

Students' Immediate Achievement Level

Table 3 presents the students' immediate achievement level when exposed to digital mind mapping application. It shows the result of the utilization of mind mapping application through pre-test and direct post test scores. This encompasses the ability of the students to attain the intended learning outcomes in a short range of time. Immediate achievement is comparable to the short-term mastery of the students in acquiring new knowledge.

Table 3. Students' Immediate Achievement in Relation to Pretest and Direct Post-test Scores

Score Range	Pretest		Direct Post-test		Descriptive Rating
	N	%	N	%	
16.8-20.0	0	0	0	0	Outstanding
15.2-16.7	0	0	0	0	Very Satisfactory
13.6-15.1	0	0	2	6	Satisfactory
12.0-13.5	0	0	5	14	Fairly Satisfactory
0.00-11.9	36	100	29	80	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	36	100	36	100	
Overall Mean	6.67		8.72		
Std. Deviation	1.93		3.27		
Descriptor	DNME		DNME		

Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
16.8-20.0	Outstanding	Outstanding Immediate Achievement
15.2-16.7	Very Satisfactory	Very Satisfying Immediate Achievement
13.6-15.1	Satisfactory	Satisfying Immediate Achievement
12.0-13.5	Fairly Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfying Immediate Achievement
0.00-11.9	Did Not Meet Expectations	Poor Immediate Achievement

The pretest scores highlight the baseline level of proficiency among the students prior to the intervention. It further reveals that 100 percent of the students, with a total number of 36 students, scored below 12. This shows an overall mean of 6.67 and standard deviation of 1.93. The students' result in their pretest suggests a clear need for intervention such as the digital mind mapping application in improving student outcomes.

On the other hand, the direct post-test scores of the students depict a positive outcome after the utilization of mind mapping application. The percentage of the students who scored below 12 declined to 80 percent. Moreover, some students show progress in their performance. Five students (14 percent) obtained a fairly satisfying achievement level while 2 students (6 percent) garnered a satisfying achievement level. The overall mean of students' direct post-test scores is 8.72 and standard deviation of 3.27. Notwithstanding the increase in students' performance from pretest to direct post-test, the

achievement level is still not satisfactory. The immediate achievement level of the students in terms of pretest and direct post-test scores did not meet the expectations and interpreted as “poor” immediate achievement.

This outcome corresponds with the Philippine ranking in the Programme for International Assessment (PISA) 2018. According to the result, only 22% of the 7, 233 15-year-old Filipino students who participated in PISA achieved the minimum level of competency in science literacy. This performance in the science assessment places the Philippines near the bottom of the 79 countries and economies that participated in PISA 2018. This shows that Filipino students have poor immediate achievement as reflected in their poor academic performance.

As observed during the implementation of the study, the poor immediate achievement of the students may be influenced by their poor reading skills and comprehension, as well as their short attention span. According to the study of Imam (2016), regular reading is suggested to enhance comprehension and boost student performance. It indicates that the students’ ability to read highly affect their comprehension and performance. Additionally, independent reading often fosters strong comprehension skills and critical thinking abilities. The benefits extend beyond academia, as reading skills acquired in youth persist into adulthood. However, individuals with limited attention spans face challenges in deeply engaging with academic materials, leading to fragmented learning experiences and compromised comprehension. Whether listening to lectures, tackling dense textbooks, or solving complex problems, their ability to sustain focus is hindered, impacting their capacity for meaningful understanding (Akbasli et al., 2016). Shortened attention spans correlate with lower test scores, difficulty retaining information, and struggles in synthesizing disparate concepts into cohesive understanding.

Students’ Knowledge Retention Level

Table 4 exhibits the outcome with regard to students' retention of knowledge when exposed to digital mind mapping application. This displays the percentage and score range of the students who received direct post-test and a delayed post-test intervention. This section will reveal the ability of the students to recall and retain knowledge four weeks after the intervention, with the direct post-test serving as our baseline.

The same data are used for the direct post-test, wherein the overall mean is 8.72 and standard deviation of 3.27. Table 4 further reveals that the majority of students (24 out of 36 students, constituting 66 percent) still scored below 12 in their delayed post-test. Most of the students did not meet expectations. Delayed post-test result exhibits notable findings. Specifically, five students (14 percent) garnered fairly satisfying scores and another five students (14 percent) secured satisfying scores. Furthermore, a new result was obtained wherein one student attained very satisfying score and another one who got an outstanding score. Regardless of this progress, with an overall mean of 10.53 and standard deviation of 3.35, the knowledge retention level of the students is still not satisfactory. The knowledge retention level of the students in terms of direct post-test and

delayed post-test scores did not meet the expectations and interpreted as “poor” knowledge retention.

Table 4. Students’ Knowledge Retention in Relation to Direct Post-test and Delayed Post-test

Score Range	Direct Post-test		Delayed Post-test		Descriptive Rating
	N	%	N	%	
16.8-20.0	0	0	1	3	Outstanding
15.2-16.7	0	0	1	3	Very Satisfactory
13.6-15.1	2	6	5	14	Satisfactory
12.0-13.5	5	14	5	14	Fairly Satisfactory
0.00-11.9	29	80	24	66	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	36	100	36	100	
Overall Mean	8.72		10.53		
Std. Deviation	3.27		3.35		
Descriptor	DNME		DNME		

Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
16.8-20.0	Outstanding	Outstanding Knowledge Retention
15.2-16.7	Very Satisfactory	Very Satisfying Knowledge Retention
13.6-15.1	Satisfactory	Satisfying Knowledge Retention
12.0-13.5	Fairly Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfying Knowledge Retention
0.00-11.9	Did Not Meet Expectations	Poor Knowledge Retention

This outcome affirms the investigation of Dumale and Gurat (2023) stating that Grade 12 students enrolled in the course subject 'statistics and probability' exhibited a poor retention rate in solving sample problems and sample probabilities. Furthermore, they noted that students demonstrated a poor retention rate across all learning competencies related to sampling distribution of the sample mean, with the exception of illustrating random sampling.

Retention of information is a crucial aspect of the learning process. One major factor that affects the students’ poor retention is having poor note-taking strategies. Benzer et al. (2022) defines note-taking as summarizing what one has understood in one's own words to remember it later. As observed during the implementation of the study, many students don’t know the most effective way to take notes in class. As a result, students are often left with study notes that are missing information, hard to understand, or unorganized (Peverly & Wolf, 2019). Furthermore, Peverly and Wolf’s study indicates that students who actively engage with the material while taking notes have the chance to deeply encode the information into their memory.

Inferential Analysis on Students’ Immediate Achievement Level

Table 5 depicts the paired t-test analysis on students’ immediate achievement when exposed to digital mind mapping application. It shows the effect of the utilization of mind mapping application through analyzing the difference between the students’ pre-test and direct post test scores. This result aims to reject the first null hypothesis stating that

there is no significant difference in students' immediate achievement level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test.

Table 5. Paired T-test Analysis on Students' Immediate Achievement Level

	Paired Difference		t	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Direct posttest- Pretest	2.0556	3.2509	3.7939	0.0006**

It resulted in a mean difference of 2.0556, a standard deviation of 3.2509, and a t-value of 3.7939. It indicates that significant number of students showcased improvements in direct post-test. The overall mean scores from pretest to direct post-test increased from 6.67 ± 1.93 to 8.72 ± 3.27 . With a p-value of 0.0006, this manifests a highly significant enhancement in students' immediate achievement following the intervention of the digital mind mapping application. This implies that despite the students' initially poor achievement level, the utilization of the digital mind mapping application has a positive effect on the students' immediate achievement in terms of pretest and direct post-test.

Mind mapping effectively enhances students' immediate achievement because of its collaborative feature for brainstorming and seamlessness to construct ideas. According to a study by Suharto et al. (2023), the implementation of mind maps significantly enhances learners' ability to grasp material more rapidly, thereby saving time during collaborative tasks. Additionally, mind mapping helps students to better understand the relationships between different concepts, which facilitates deeper comprehension. As it encourages active participation and a clearer visualization of ideas. The collaborative nature of mind mapping thus not only fosters a more interactive learning environment but also contributes to more efficient and effective educational outcomes. Collaboration significantly enhances student performance, as evidenced by the study conducted by Chan and Ko (2019). The research indicates that interactivity within collaborative learning environments markedly improves learners' outcomes.

This outcome reinforces the study of Bawaneh (2019) who investigated the effectiveness of mind maps compared to conventional teaching methods for Jordanian tenth graders learning electric energy concepts. The results revealed that students who learned using mind maps exhibited significantly greater immediate achievement and retention of electric energy concepts compared to those using conventional methods. In the local context, the result also supports the study of Geolin (2024) who assessed the status of mind mapping as a strategy in teaching Grade 7 Chemistry at Zapatera National High School, Sikatuna St., Brgy. Zapatera, Cebu City, Cebu, Philippines. The result states that Mind Mapping as a strategy evidently showed a vital connection to the improvement of Junior High School performance in Chemistry. It is more effective in both teaching and learning process as compared to the chalk talk method.

Inferential Analysis on Students' Knowledge Retention Level

Table 6 portrays the paired t-test analysis on students' knowledge retention when exposed to digital mind mapping application. It shows the effect of the utilization of mind mapping application through analyzing the difference between the students' direct post test and delayed post-test scores. This result aims to reject the second null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in students' knowledge retention level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test.

Table 6. Paired T-test Analysis on Students' Knowledge Retention Level

	Paired Difference		t	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Delayed Posttest- Direct Posttest	1.8046	2.4590	4.4055	0.0000**

The data shows a mean difference of 1.8046, a standard deviation of 2.4590, and a t-value of 4.4055. It reveals that there is a significant difference between the students' pre-test and direct post test scores. The overall mean scores from direct post-test to delayed post-test increased from 8.72 ± 3.27 to 10.53 ± 3.35 . With a highly statistically significant p-value of 0.0000, the increase in average scores from direct post-test to delayed post-test unveils a significant positive effect of the utilization of mind mapping application in enhancing students' knowledge retention in science or their ability to retain knowledge over time. This conveys that despite the students' initially poor retention level, the utilization of the digital mind mapping application significantly contributed to the improvement of students' knowledge retention level.

The positive effect of digital mind mapping application lies in the fact that it is an effective note-taking tool for studying and accessible for tech-savvy 21st century learners. According to the Grand Canyon University (2023), technology can transform classrooms into engaging environments. One-to-one device initiatives allow for a smoother integration of tech into lessons, while interactive software and gamified learning with badges and achievements make lectures, responses, and the overall learning process more fun and motivating for students. According to the study of Flietstra (2023), students performed most highly when they were given autonomy in their notetaking style or were told exactly what to write down. It was found that students who took notes using mind maps scored higher on an achievement test than students who took notes traditionally. The study concludes that mind mapping is an effective note-taking strategy (Madu & Metu, 2012). Moreover, mind maps were more effective than concept maps for learning organic chemistry (Imam & Olorundare, 2023). Lastly, in the study about the impact of educational technology on students' performance in secondary schools, students reported mostly positive experiences with educational technology (Murad et al., 2019).

The results of this study are consistent with the analysis of Akanbi et al. (2021) who investigated the effectiveness of mind maps in improving physics knowledge

retention for senior secondary school students. The findings revealed that students who learned with mind maps exhibited significantly better retention compared to the control group who used conventional methods. Additionally, the study of Nacilla and Dolotallas (2019) revealed that forty Grade 8 students of Cabalantian National High School who learned with mind maps scored significantly higher on the posttest compared to the lecture group in Biology.

Conclusions

The students' level of immediate achievement is poor. Eighty percent of the students failed to meet the intended learning outcomes.

Students have a poor level of knowledge retention. Sixty-six percent of the students have a low span of retention and are unable to reach the expected rate of retention.

The inferential analysis rejects the first null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in students' immediate achievement level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of pretest and direct post-test. These findings provide strong evidence that the digital mind mapping application has effectively contributed to enhancing student achievement levels.

The paired t-test analysis rejects the second null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in students' knowledge retention level exposed to digital mind mapping application in terms of direct post-test and delayed post-test. This significant increase in scores from the direct post-test to delayed post-test suggests that the digital mind mapping application effectively enhanced students' ability to retain knowledge over time.

Recommendations

The result of this study reveals poor immediate achievement level and poor knowledge retention level among students. This calls the attention of higher authority, experts, and educators to give ample consideration and effort in enhancing students' ability to immediately acquire knowledge and retain information. As per obtained results, the researchers would like to recommend to consider utilizing digital mind mapping as a method in maximizing the students' immediate achievement and retention level. This recommendation aims to leverage technology, specifically mobile applications, to promote effective presentation of information, knowledge construction, collaboration, and note-taking practices among students in the classroom setting.

This study suggests that further research should employ quasi-experimental design to explore the effectiveness of digital mind mapping application in optimizing learning outcomes. Additionally, researchers recommend investigating the correlation between immediate achievement and knowledge retention under the intervention of digital mind mapping application. Moreover, this study proposes to determine the

significant difference in the effectiveness between digital mind maps and conventional mind maps. Furthermore, this study hypothesizes that a student's learning style may influence how well mind mapping benefits their learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the implementation of the study, researchers applied for a research permit from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) and asked for approval from the school head to formally conduct the study. Additionally, the researchers requested permission from the class adviser for assistance in conducting the research and provided the participants with the consent form to ensure their voluntary participation and safeguard their rights throughout the research. All the participants were Grade 7 Archimedes students enrolled in Tongantongan National High School, with their identities hidden, and accessible only to the researchers. The study was conducted within a school government institution, prioritizing privacy and confidentiality. Only the researchers had access to participants' information, ensuring clarity by providing only the necessary questionnaires. Although the research caused specific risks, especially involving students and the school, it also presented benefits for both researchers and institutions. It offered recommended solutions to identified problems within the institution, enabling the management to create trust and confidence in the researchers.

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